

RISK AND CONSENT FORM

SHARAD PAWAR DENTAL COLLEGE AND HOSPITAL

SAWANGI (MEGHE), WARDHA

DEPARTMENT OF ORAL & MAXILLOFACIAL PATHOLOGY & MICROBIOLOGY

I _____ Age _____ Sex _____

resident of _____ render this Risk Consent in full sanity without any compulsion of any kind .I had been explained by doctor , department of Oral & Maxillofacial Pathology & Microbiology in detail in my own language regarding the disease need of blood investigation, incisional biopsy and examination of lesion. So, I understand that I am fully responsible for risks pertaining to any treatment/investigation/procedure there on during the management of my own self/my ward. I am signing the risk consent in full sanity and consciousness without any compulsion.

WITNESS: _____

NAME: _____

SIGN OR THUMB IMPRESSION:

DATE:

PLACE:

TIME:

SIGNED IN PRESENCE OF DOCTOR/NURSE